

Epigenetic Architecture of ccRCC: Functional Roles of Long Non-coding RNAs and Therapeutic Potential

Anna Chumakova^{#1,*}, Gulfiya Yumaguzhina^{#2}, Alsu Gabdullina^{#2}, Diluza Gumerova^{#2}, Elza Khusnutdinova^{#1,2}, Irina Gilyazova^{#1,2}

^{#1} Institute of Biochemistry and Genetics—Subdivision of the Ufa Federal Research Centre of the Russian Academy of Sciences (IBG UFRC RAS), Ufa, Russia

^{#2} Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Bashkir State Medical University» of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, Ufa, Russia

Abstract— Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) is a heterogeneous malignancy with diverse histological subtypes and complex genetic and epigenetic landscapes; clear cell RCC (ccRCC) accounts for roughly 80% of cases. Despite advances in surgery, targeted therapy, and immune checkpoint inhibitors, treatment of advanced and recurrent ccRCC remains limited by intertumoral heterogeneity, genomic instability, and an immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment. Epigenetic regulators, particularly long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), have emerged as key modulators of ccRCC pathogenesis. lncRNAs (>200 nt) participate in transcriptional and post-transcriptional control, chromatin remodeling, three-dimensional genome organization, and act as competing endogenous RNAs (ceRNAs) for microRNAs, thereby influencing metabolic reprogramming, DNA repair, cell cycle progression, apoptosis, and metastatic behavior. Recent multiomic and single-cell studies, including TCGA analyses, reveal that dysregulated lncRNAs can function as oncogenes (e.g., promoting glycolysis, genomic instability, and metastasis) or tumor suppressors (e.g., inhibiting c-Myc signaling, inducing apoptosis). Several lncRNA signatures correlate with prognosis and therapeutic targets. However, functional characterization of many ccRCC-associated lncRNAs remains incomplete, and clinical translation requires validation in large, prospective cohorts and mechanistic studies. Continued integration of genomics, epigenomics, and single-cell approaches will be essential to harness lncRNAs for personalized management of RCC.

Keywords— clear cell renal-cell carcinoma, long non-coding RNAs, oncogenes, tumor suppressors, ccRCC pathogenesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) is a heterogeneous group of cancers with a complex genetic background and histological subtypes that require different clinical treatment approaches [1]. RCC encompasses a wide range of histopathological subtypes. Clear cell renal cell carcinoma (ccRCC) accounts for approximately 80% of cases.

Kidney cancer is the 14th most common cancer worldwide [2] and the 10th most common in Russia [3]. According to data presented on The Global Cancer Observatory (GCO), an interactive web platform with global cancer statistics focused on visualizing cancer indicators using data from various sources, in 2022, the incidence of kidney cancer was 434,743 cases worldwide, with 29,109 cases occurring in the Russian Federation. Mortality rates were 155,915 and 9,148 cases, respectively [4]. Tables I and II present detailed information on incidence and mortality rates for renal cell carcinoma in the 10 countries with the highest rates.

CcRCC is a disease characterized by a potentially high degree of tumor heterogeneity and a hereditary predisposition, driven by mutations in genes involved in the regulation of cellular metabolism [5]. Molecular biology and genetic studies of sporadic ccRCC have led to a better understanding of its pathogenesis and development; it is believed that all forms of RCC exhibit structural alterations in chromosome 3p21 [1], [5]. The carcinogenesis of ccRCC is a complex biological process closely associated with gene mutations, genomic instability, and epigenetic dysregulation [6]. Epigenetic dysregulation involves multiple factors, including DNA methylation, histone modification, genomic instability, and gene mutations [7].

The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) project has made a significant contribution to the study of ccRCC, conducting research on DNA, RNA, proteins, and metabolic pathways in a large-scale sample of ccRCC patients, revealing that heterogeneous ccRCC tumors can evolve into cell clusters with distinct genomic profiles. Further research on single-cell RNA sequencing revealed to researchers the characteristics of tumor cells, tumor-specific markers, and the tumor's immune microenvironment at the single-cell level [5].

Radical nephrectomy or partial nephrectomy are considered the standard of care for kidney cancer; however, for patients who, for various reasons, are not candidates for surgery, alternative approaches such as radiofrequency ablation and cryoablation have been developed. Neither surgical nor ablation approaches preclude the occurrence of recurrence [8]. Approximately 20–30% of patients experience recurrence within

2 years after radical nephrectomy, and nearly all of these recurrences are extremely resistant to both chemotherapy and radiation therapy [6].

TABLE I
Incidence in 2022 by kidney cancer [4]

Countries	Incidence		
	Both sexes	Males	Females
China	73 656	47 306	26 350
United States of America	71 759	46 549	25 210
Russian Federation	29 109	16 882	12 227
Japan	21 207	14 875	6 332
Germany	20 514	12 933	7 581
India	17 480	11 094	6 386
France (metropolitan)	14 541	9 253	5 288
United Kingdom	13 714	8 717	4 997
Italy	13 666	9 090	4 576
Brazil	11 090	7 048	4 042

TABLE III
Mortality in 2022 by kidney cancer [4]

Countries	Mortality		
	Both sexes	Males	Females
China	23 991	16 390	7 601
United States of America	14 295	9 519	4 776
India	10 464	6 686	3 778
Russian Federation	9 148	5 493	3 655
Germany	7 856	5 025	2 831
Japan	6 926	4 461	2 465
France (metropolitan)	5 058	3 349	1 709
United Kingdom	4 736	2 979	1 757
Italy	4 592	2 914	1 678
Brazil	4 460	2 814	1 646

In the adjuvant setting, the effects of several factors were investigated: cytokine therapy, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs), and mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) inhibitors. The results were inconclusive, as significant toxicity and a lack of proven benefit for overall survival (OS) cast doubt on the appropriateness of their use in routine practice. The promising results of KEYNOTE 564 were accompanied by a series of parallel negative adjuvant trials investigating other ICIs. The trials differed in eligibility criteria, treatment, and design. These negative studies have sparked debate regarding whether immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) are effective in adjuvant therapy for RCC. There are many nuances that may explain the negative results, which are beyond the scope of this review. Currently, adjuvant pembrolizumab is the only ICI approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for resected resectable RCC. Highly sensitive biomarkers of minimal residual disease will allow for the identification of patients who are most likely to benefit from adjuvant therapy, while sparing those who were cured by surgery alone from unnecessary treatment-related toxicity without oncological benefit [8].

In recent years, immune checkpoint inhibitor (ICI) therapy has proven effective in the treatment of renal cell carcinoma. It has been shown that neoadjuvant therapy with ICIs prior to nephrectomy reduces the stage of high-risk renal cell carcinoma tumors (e.g., large inoperable renal mass, a tumor thrombus invading the inferior vena cava), although there is currently no approved standard neoadjuvant therapy for renal cell carcinoma. Given the success of ICI in advanced disease, it has been hypothesized that neoadjuvant ICI may elicit a strong immune response, with the intact primary tumor providing a high antigenic load. Two small studies investigating ICI monotherapy have demonstrated the safety of the neoadjuvant approach in RCC. Several neoadjuvant trials for renal cell carcinoma are currently underway, investigating ICI-based combinations [8]. Over the past few decades, thanks to the rapid development of targeted and immunotherapy drugs, therapeutic options for patients with advanced RCC have expanded significantly. Unfortunately, the efficacy of these treatments for patients with advanced or metastatic ccRCC remains very limited, primarily due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the tumor microenvironment [6].

There is a need to study biomarkers capable of indicating the nature of a tumor and predicting the outcome of treatment. MicroRNAs are among such molecular markers.

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a subclass of small non-coding RNAs (sncRNAs), which are small single-stranded RNA molecules that function exclusively at the post-transcriptional level. miRNAs can induce transcriptional silencing of target genes by binding to their 3'-untranslated region (3'UTR) sequences. More importantly, a growing number of studies have found that miRNAs interact closely with lncRNAs. [6].

Current researchers are paying close attention to the role of the lncRNA/miRNA/mRNA axis in the pathogenesis of advanced gastric cancer, as studying this issue may aid in the discovery of new, more effective biomarkers and therapeutic targets for advanced gastric cancer. The lncRNA/miRNA/mRNA axis plays a crucial role in the initiation and progression of various carcinomas, such as ccRCC. Studies have shown that certain oncogenic miRNAs are upregulated in ccRCC, while certain tumor-suppressor miRNAs are downregulated. In this case, lncRNAs that bind to oncogenic miRNAs will lead to tumor inhibition, while those that interact with suppressor miRNAs will have the opposite effect on the tumor [6].

MiRNAs, their functions, and their impact on carcinogenesis have already been fairly well studied. Currently, researchers are focusing on the role of lncRNAs in the pathogenesis of gastric cancer; however, their role remains largely unclear. This highlights the need for in-depth research into long non-coding RNAs, their functions, and their applications.

Objective: This review was conducted to analyse and update information on long non-coding RNAs and their impact on the carcinogenesis of clear cell renal cell carcinoma.

II. NON-CODING RNAs

Epigenetics is the study of changes in genetic function that are not inherited and do not involve changes in DNA sequences. There are three main mechanisms of epigenetics: non-coding RNAs, histone modifications, and DNA methylation. Genome analysis has shown that nearly 98% of the genome (in eukaryotes) is transcribed into non-coding RNAs and less than 2% into proteins. Non-coding RNAs include “housekeeping” RNAs, such as ribosomal RNA (rRNA), transfer RNA (tRNA), and regulatory RNAs, which are divided into two categories based on transcript length [1]. It was originally believed that non-coding RNAs had no effect on the human body, but it is now known that non-coding RNAs influence gene expression and regulation through various molecular mechanisms, thereby affecting the onset and progression of many diseases [9].

Non-coding RNAs are RNAs that cannot be translated into proteins; they include long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs), microRNAs (miRNAs or miRs), circular RNAs, and small nuclear RNAs [7].

III. LONG NON-CODING RNAs

Long non-coding RNAs are non-coding RNA sequences longer than 200 nucleotides [10]. They are transcribed by RNA polymerase II and sometimes by RNA polymerase III, and undergo 5'-terminal capping, pre-splicing, and polyadenylation [11], [12]. lncRNAs were long considered unstable structures, but a number of studies have revealed that most long non-coding RNAs are stable; their stabilization occurs primarily through polyadenylation, while others are stabilized by the formation of secondary structures, such as triple-helix structures at their 3'-ends, or tertiary structures [11], [12], [13], [14].

lncRNAs can be divided into several types: long intergenic non-coding RNAs, enhancer RNAs, intronic RNAs, and antisense lncRNAs [12].

lncRNAs influence many cellular processes, such as the cell cycle, cell differentiation, and metabolism, as well as the onset and progression of diseases [14]. It has been demonstrated that lncRNAs may play a role in the development of viral infectious diseases [14], [15]. lncRNAs attract the interest of researchers due to their various mechanisms of action; for example, they are capable of modulating processes such as transcription, translation, and post-translational modifications of DNA, RNA, or proteins, as well as epigenetic modifications and the stabilization of proteins or RNA [14]. lncRNAs are also capable of interacting directly with signaling receptors [14], [16].

lncRNAs epigenetically regulate and modify chromatin structures through acetylation and methylation by specific enzymes, including enzymes that modify DNA and histones, and proteins associated with chromatin organization [12], [17]. lncRNAs are involved in modulating three-dimensional genomic architecture [12], [18].

It has been noted that although lncRNAs are expressed at lower levels than mRNAs, they exhibit more pronounced tissue-specific expression patterns, suggesting that they perform specific functions depending on cell type [14], [19], [20]. The differences between lncRNAs and mRNAs reflect the fact that lncRNAs themselves constitute functional units guided by local molecular interactions to maintain homeostasis in cells [14].

Technologies are advancing rapidly and enable the rapid identification of new lncRNAs and their regulatory mechanisms in carcinogenesis. Understanding the epigenetic and epitranscriptomic regulation of lncRNAs may help unravel the molecular mechanisms contributing to the development and progression of cancer [12].

IV. LONG NON-CODING RNAs IN ccRCC

In the pathogenesis of clear cell renal cell carcinoma, long non-coding RNAs can serve as oncogenes and tumor suppressors (Figure 1).

Fig. 1 The dual nature of the effect of long non-coding RNAs in ccRCC

A. lncRNAs as Oncogenes

lncRNAs regulate chromatin structures and oncogene expression by directly recruiting epigenetic and epitranscriptional regulators, thereby contributing to tumor development and progression [12].

Tumor cells undergo multiple metabolic changes, leading to the accumulation of metabolites and byproducts that facilitate their rapid proliferation and invasion under nutrient-deprived conditions [21], [22], [23], [24]. It has been suggested that abnormally enhanced glycolysis is associated with a poor prognosis for ccRCC, and thus may be a potential diagnostic and therapeutic target. Li et al. [25] identified such lncRNAs (AC156455.1, AC009084.1, and LINC00342) and, based on them, stratified patients into risk groups with high sensitivity and specificity; their findings correlated with overall poor survival in patients with advanced ccRCC [22], [25]. In this regard, it has been proposed that lncRNAs may regulate the expression of glycolytic enzymes, thereby influencing glycolytic activity and tumor cell proliferation, through their ability to interact with transcription factor receptors [22], [26], [27]. It has also been noted that lncRNAs can induce the degradation of certain glycolytic enzymes via ubiquitination [22], [28]. The modulation of glycolytic pathways by lncRNAs may be based on interaction with specific microRNAs. lncRNAs acts on them as a sponge or competitive RNA; as a result of this inhibition, changes occur in glycolysis. Studies by Zhao et al. [29] have shown that lncRNA can metabolically reprogram cells, leading to sustained glycolysis, as well as enhanced invasion and metastasis [22].

The development of cancer is associated with mutations in DNA repair genes, leading to genomic instability, which accounts for tumor heterogeneity and serves as an indicator of tumor progression and prognosis. Results from a number of studies have shown that lncRNAs are involved in maintaining genomic stability [22], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34].

Single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) have been found to be prevalent in tumors and occur in ncRNAs, particularly lncRNAs, leading to their aberrant function or expression [22], [35], [36]. It has been shown that lncRNA regulates the mitotic checkpoint and centromeric proteins [22], [37], [38]. It has been suggested that chromosomal instability and tumorigenesis are associated with increased regulation of lncRNA containing telomeric repeats and the subsequent stabilization of shortened telomeres [22], [34], [39]. Disruption of topologically associated domains (TADs) through genomic rearrangements can lead to abnormal gene expression and disease development; properly functioning lncRNAs can prevent such damage through stabilization [22], [40], [41], [42].

DNA alterations, particularly those leading to defective repair of double-strand breaks (DSBs), are associated with tumorigenesis [22], [43]. A number of studies have shown that certain damage-induced lncRNAs can be considered key regulators of aberrant DSB repair, leading to genomic instability and cancer development. The role of lncRNAs derived from genomic instability in RCC has not been widely studied; however, one study suggested that the following lncRNAs—LINC00460, AL139351.1, AC156455.1, AL035446.1, LINC02471, AC022509.2, and LINC01606, may be involved in the cell cycle, DNA replication, mismatch repair, and, consequently, in the development and progression of ccRCC. However, to date, some of these RNAs have not been associated with any tumors [22], [34], [43].

Another study suggested that the combination of miRNAs is closely correlated with distant metastases in advanced colorectal cancer and with prognosis. This combination included LINC01234, LINC02577, and LINC02609. The first lncRNA has been reported to be significantly elevated in certain types of cancer, but there is no information on the role of LINC02577 and LINC02609 in human cancer. In a study conducted by Su et al. [44], the aforementioned lncRNA promoted distant metastasis of ccRCC through a mechanism involving the regulation of autophagy. The authors suggested that a set of lncRNAs associated with distant metastases could serve not only as a reliable prognostic biomarker but also as a promising therapeutic target for advanced ccRCC [22], [44].

The expression level of the ITGB1 lncRNA, as an oncogene, was significantly higher in advanced ccRCC than in other samples and correlates with the survival of patients with ccRCC, but its exact role in the development and progression of the disease remains unclear. A research group led by Zheng et al. found that MCL-1 expression in ccRCC tissues positively correlated with ITGB1 expression, promoting normal mitochondrial fusion, rapid ATP production, sustaining energy supply to ccRCC, and contributing to tumorigenesis [21].

B. LncRNA as Tumor Suppressors

Recent studies have shown that Myc-dependent metabolic reprogramming is a key factor in tumorigenesis. C-Myc is an important member of the Myc gene family and plays a crucial role in many biological processes, including the cell cycle, cell proliferation, apoptosis, and cellular metabolism. It has been reported that c-MYC is significantly activated in ccRCC and can directly regulate the expression of glucose metabolism genes or induce glycolysis-related metabolic enzymes to increase glucose uptake and synthesis [21], [45]. It is known that lncRNAs can promote the transcription of their host genes or protect their homologous mRNAs from miRNA-mediated degradation by inhibiting miRNA activity (as ceRNAs). For example, the SARCC (suppression of androgen receptor in renal cell carcinoma) lncRNA acts as a ceRNA to suppress the expression of Mir-143-3p. Inhibition of the function of the unstable androgen receptor (AR) protein inhibits downstream signaling, including AKT, MMP-13, K-RAS, and P-ERK [21], [46]. In addition, lncRNA SARCC can also inhibit the progression of the hypoxic cell cycle in VHL-mutant RCC cells and inhibit the AR/HIF-2 α /C-MYC signaling pathway by physically binding to and destabilizing the AR protein, thereby post-transcriptionally regulating AR to form a negative feedback regulatory mechanism [21]. LncRNAs mediate cell cycle arrest and apoptosis by regulating the expression of cyclin-associated proteins (such as cyclin D1, p53, and P16) and apoptosis-associated proteins (such as Bax and Bcl-2). Yang et al. [47] found that the lncRNA KCNQ1DN was significantly downregulated in ccRCC tissues and cell lines, and gene analysis revealed that KCNQ1DN can influence downstream genes such as GLUTs and HK2 by

inhibiting the transcriptional activity of c-MyC gene promoters, thereby impeding glucose uptake, inhibiting the glycolytic pathway, and reducing energy supply [47]. Furthermore, cyclin D1 is an important target of c-MyC in the cell cycle, and KCNQ1DN further enhances the regulation of cyclin D1 in RCC cells and induces cell cycle arrest in tumor cells [21].

MCL-1 is a member of the BCL-2 family of anti-apoptotic proteins with a short half-life and one of the most frequently amplified genes in cancer; it is a potential key factor in the regulation of apoptosis and controls the early events of the associated cascade response leading to the release of cytochrome c. MCL-1 exhibits different functions at different mitochondrial locations: on the outer mitochondrial membrane, its isoform counteracts apoptosis, as do other BCL-2 anti-apoptotic molecules, whereas in the mitochondrial matrix, the N-terminal isoform of MCL-1 promotes normal mitochondrial fusion, ATP production, membrane potential, respiration, cristae ultrastructure, and oligomeric ATP synthase activity [21], [48]. It has been established that the MEG3 (maternal-expressed gene 3) lncRNA, a tumor suppressor, is involved in cancer development [21], [49], [50]. Gong et al. found that MEG3 lncRNA mediates ST3Gal1 to regulate EGFR phosphorylation, which downregulates Bcl-2 and pre-caspase-2 expression, increases caspase-2 activity and cytochrome c release, leading to mitochondrial dysfunction and inducing apoptosis in ccRCC cells [21], [51]. It has been observed that HOTAIR not only participates in the glycolysis of ccRCC cells but also mediates mitochondrial apoptosis. HOTAIR lncRNA induces mitochondrial calcium-dependent death 1 (MICU1)-dependent cell death in ccRCC cells by modulating mitochondria-associated cell death pathways, such as Bcl-2, BAX, and cytochrome c, and by altering the mitochondrial membrane potential [21], [52].

V. CONCLUSIONS

Long non-coding RNAs are promising diagnostic, prognostic, and therapeutic biomarkers due to their oncogenic and tumor-suppressive nature. They serve as important epigenetic regulators (controlling transcriptional and post-transcriptional processes, modifying chromatin and the 3D structure of the genome), act as ceRNAs for miRNAs, influence metabolic pathways within the cell, thereby altering the cell cycle, proliferation, and spread, and modulating apoptosis. LncRNAs are tissue-specific and heterogeneous; further fundamental research is needed with the aim of applying the results in translational studies for implementation in clinical practice.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work was performed within the framework of the State Assignment (№ 125012900944-7) of the IBG UFRC RAS.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Grammatikaki *et al.*, 'An Overview of Epigenetics in Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma', *In Vivo*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2023, doi: 10.21873/invivo.13049.
- [2] 'World Cancer Research Fund', World Cancer Research Fund. Accessed: Jun. 01, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wcrf.org/>
- [3] А. Д. Каприн, В. В. Старинский, and А. О. Шахзадова, *ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫЕ НОВООБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РОССИИ В 2023 ГОДУ (ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТЬ И СМЕРТНОСТЬ)*. Москва: МНИОИ им. П.А. Герцена – филиал ФГБУ «НМИЦ радиологии» Минздрава России, 2024. [Pdf]. Available: <https://oncology-association.ru/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/zis-2023-elektronnaya-versiya.pdf>
- [4] 'The Global Cancer Observatory (GCO)', The Global Cancer Observatory (GCO). Accessed: Jun. 01, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://gco.iarc.who.int/>
- [5] Z. Yu *et al.*, 'Integrative Single-Cell Analysis Reveals Transcriptional and Epigenetic Regulatory Features of Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Cancer Res*, vol. 83, no. 5, pp. 700–719, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-22-2224.
- [6] Q. Zhang, H. Ren, L. Ge, W. Zhang, F. Song, and P. Huang, 'A review on the role of long non-coding RNA and microRNA network in clear cell renal cell carcinoma and its tumor microenvironment', *Cancer Cell Int*, vol. 23, no. 1, p. 16, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1186/s12935-023-02861-6.
- [7] Z. Su, J. Ao, F. Zhao, G. Xu, H. Chen, and C. Gao, 'The roles of long non-coding RNAs in renal cell carcinoma (Review)', *Mol Clin Oncol*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. 4, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3892/mco.2022.2600.
- [8] Y.-W. Chen *et al.*, 'Treatment Landscape of Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Curr Treat Options Oncol*, vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 1889–1916, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11864-023-01161-5.
- [9] Y. Liu, H. Zhang, Y. Fang, D. Tang, and Z. Luo, 'Non-coding RNAs in renal cell carcinoma: Implications for drug resistance', *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 164, p. 115001, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.biopha.2023.115001.
- [10] G. Li, B. Wang, L. Ye, and G. Wang, 'Exploring Long Noncoding RNAs as Regulators of Tumor Ferroptosis: Advances and Challenges', *Cancer Sci*, vol. 116, no. 7, pp. 1795–1806, Jul. 2025, doi: 10.1111/cas.70074.
- [11] Z. Kang, L. Zhang, and Z. Yang, 'Role of non-coding RNAs in the pathogenesis of viral myocarditis', *Virulence*, vol. 16, no. 1, p. 2466480, Dec. 2025, doi: 10.1080/21505594.2025.2466480.
- [12] C. Dai, H. Qianjiang, R. Fu, H. Yang, A. Shi, and H. Luo, 'Epigenetic and epitranscriptomic role of lncRNA in carcinogenesis (Review)', *Int J Oncol*, vol. 66, no. 4, p. 29, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.3892/ijo.2025.5735.
- [13] A. Esmacili, N. Yazdanpanah, and N. Rezaei, 'LncRNAs Orchestrating Neuroinflammation: A Comprehensive Review', *Cell Mol Neurobiol*, vol. 45, no. 1, p. 21, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1007/s10571-025-01538-0.

- [14] M. C. Bridges, A. C. Daulagala, and A. Kourtidis, 'LNCcation: lncRNA localization and function', *J Cell Biol*, vol. 220, no. 2, p. e202009045, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1083/jcb.202009045.
- [15] Y. Wang *et al.*, 'Single-cell RNA-sequencing analysis identifies host long noncoding RNA MAMDC2-AS1 as a co-factor for HSV-1 nuclear transport', *Int J Biol Sci*, vol. 16, no. 9, pp. 1586–1603, 2020, doi: 10.7150/ijbs.42556.
- [16] K. Schmidt *et al.*, 'Targeting the Oncogenic Long Non-coding RNA SLNCR1 by Blocking Its Sequence-Specific Binding to the Androgen Receptor', *Cell Rep*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 541–554.e5, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2019.12.011.
- [17] Y. Lu, Y.-T. Chan, H.-Y. Tan, S. Li, N. Wang, and Y. Feng, 'Epigenetic regulation in human cancer: the potential role of epi-drug in cancer therapy', *Mol Cancer*, vol. 19, no. 1, p. 79, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s12943-020-01197-3.
- [18] H. Tachiwana, T. Yamamoto, and N. Saitoh, 'Gene regulation by non-coding RNAs in the 3D genome architecture', *Curr Opin Genet Dev*, vol. 61, pp. 69–74, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.gde.2020.03.002.
- [19] B. Zuckerman and I. Ulitsky, 'Predictive models of subcellular localization of long RNAs', *RNA*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 557–572, May 2019, doi: 10.1261/rna.068288.118.
- [20] N. Mukherjee, L. Calviello, A. Hirsekorn, S. de Pretis, M. Pelizzola, and U. Ohler, 'Integrative classification of human coding and noncoding genes through RNA metabolism profiles', *Nat Struct Mol Biol*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 86–96, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1038/nsmb.3325.
- [21] H. Zhang *et al.*, 'Role of Metabolic Reprogramming of Long non-coding RNA in Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma', *J Cancer*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 691–705, 2022, doi: 10.7150/jca.62683.
- [22] J. Rysz, T. Konecki, B. Franczyk, J. Ławiński, and A. Gluba-Brzózka, 'The Role of Long Noncoding RNA (lncRNAs) Biomarkers in Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Int J Mol Sci*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 643, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijms24010643.
- [23] T. Uehara *et al.*, 'Serum lactate dehydrogenase is a predictive biomarker in patients with oropharyngeal cancer undergoing radiotherapy: Retrospective study on predictive factors', *Head Neck*, vol. 43, no. 10, pp. 3132–3141, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1002/hed.26814.
- [24] H. Li *et al.*, 'FBP1 regulates proliferation, metastasis, and chemoresistance by participating in C-MYC/STAT3 signaling axis in ovarian cancer', *Oncogene*, vol. 40, no. 40, pp. 5938–5949, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41388-021-01957-5.
- [25] T. Li *et al.*, 'Identification of a Three-Glycolysis-Related lncRNA Signature Correlated With Prognosis and Metastasis in Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Front Med (Lausanne)*, vol. 8, p. 777507, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fmed.2021.777507.
- [26] S. Zhu *et al.*, 'Pyruvate kinase M2 (PKM2) in cancer and cancer therapeutics', *Cancer Lett*, vol. 503, pp. 240–248, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.canlet.2020.11.018.
- [27] T. Yan *et al.*, 'Risk SNP-induced lncRNA-SLCC1 drives colorectal cancer through activating glycolysis signaling', *Signal Transduct Target Ther*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 70, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41392-020-00446-7.
- [28] C. Liu *et al.*, 'A cytoplasmic long noncoding RNA LINC00470 as a new AKT activator to mediate glioblastoma cell autophagy', *J Hematol Oncol*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 77, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1186/s13045-018-0619-z.
- [29] S. Zhao *et al.*, 'LncRNA MIR17HG promotes colorectal cancer liver metastasis by mediating a glycolysis-associated positive feedback circuit', *Oncogene*, vol. 40, no. 28, pp. 4709–4724, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41388-021-01859-6.
- [30] S. Negrini, V. G. Gorgoulis, and T. D. Halazonetis, 'Genomic instability--an evolving hallmark of cancer', *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 220–228, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1038/nrm2858.
- [31] R. A. Burrell, N. McGranahan, J. Bartek, and C. Swanton, 'The causes and consequences of genetic heterogeneity in cancer evolution', *Nature*, vol. 501, no. 7467, pp. 338–345, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1038/nature12625.
- [32] P. D. Malihi *et al.*, 'Single-Cell Circulating Tumor Cell Analysis Reveals Genomic Instability as a Distinctive Feature of Aggressive Prostate Cancer', *Clin Cancer Res*, vol. 26, no. 15, pp. 4143–4153, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-19-4100.
- [33] K. Suzuki *et al.*, 'The genomic damage estimated by arbitrarily primed PCR DNA fingerprinting is useful for the prognosis of gastric cancer', *Gastroenterology*, vol. 125, no. 5, pp. 1330–1340, Nov. 2003, doi: 10.1016/j.gastro.2003.07.006.
- [34] H. Yang, X. Xiong, and H. Li, 'Development and Interpretation of a Genomic Instability Derived lncRNAs Based Risk Signature as a Predictor of Prognosis for Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma Patients', *Front Oncol*, vol. 11, p. 678253, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fonc.2021.678253.
- [35] S. W. Cheetham, F. Gruhl, J. S. Mattick, and M. E. Dinger, 'Long noncoding RNAs and the genetics of cancer', *Br J Cancer*, vol. 108, no. 12, pp. 2419–2425, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1038/bjc.2013.233.
- [36] C. Lin and L. Yang, 'Long Noncoding RNA in Cancer: Wiring Signaling Circuitry', *Trends Cell Biol*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 287–301, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.tcb.2017.11.008.
- [37] S. Panda *et al.*, 'Noncoding RNA Glnr functions as an oncogene by associating with centrosomal proteins', *PLoS Biol*, vol. 16, no. 10, p. e2004204, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.2004204.
- [38] X. Deng *et al.*, 'Long noncoding RNA PiHL regulates p53 protein stability through GRWD1/RPL11/MDM2 axis in colorectal cancer', *Theranostics*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 265–280, 2020, doi: 10.7150/thno.36045.
- [39] Z. Deng *et al.*, 'Formation of telomeric repeat-containing RNA (TERRA) foci in highly proliferating mouse cerebellar neuronal progenitors and medulloblastoma', *J Cell Sci*, vol. 125, no. Pt 18, pp. 4383–4394, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1242/jcs.108118.
- [40] D. G. Lupiáñez, M. Spielmann, and S. Mundlos, 'Breaking TADs: How Alterations of Chromatin Domains Result in Disease', *Trends Genet*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 225–237, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.tig.2016.01.003.
- [41] T. Yamamoto and N. Saitoh, 'Non-coding RNAs and chromatin domains', *Curr Opin Cell Biol*, vol. 58, pp. 26–33, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ceb.2018.12.005.
- [42] J.-F. Xiang *et al.*, 'Human colorectal cancer-specific CCAT1-L lncRNA regulates long-range chromatin interactions at the MYC locus', *Cell Res*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 513–531, May 2014, doi: 10.1038/cr.2014.35.
- [43] L. Shen *et al.*, 'LncRNA lnc-RI regulates homologous recombination repair of DNA double-strand breaks by stabilizing RAD51 mRNA as a competitive endogenous RNA', *Nucleic Acids Res*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 717–729, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1093/nar/gkx1224.
- [44] Y. Su *et al.*, 'Construction of Competitive Endogenous RNA Network and Verification of 3-Key lncRNA Signature Associated With Distant Metastasis and Poor Prognosis in Patients With Clear Cell Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Front Oncol*, vol. 11, p. 640150, 2021, doi: 10.3389/fonc.2021.640150.
- [45] A. M. Gouw *et al.*, 'The MYC Oncogene Cooperates with Sterol-Regulated Element-Binding Protein to Regulate Lipogenesis Essential for Neoplastic Growth', *Cell Metab*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 556–572.e5, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.cmet.2019.07.012.
- [46] W. Zhai *et al.*, 'LncRNA-SARCC suppresses renal cell carcinoma (RCC) progression via altering the androgen receptor (AR)/miRNA-143-3p signals', *Cell Death Differ*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 1502–1517, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1038/cdd.2017.74.
- [47] F. Yang *et al.*, 'The long noncoding RNA KCNQ1DN suppresses the survival of renal cell carcinoma cells through downregulating c-Myc', *J Cancer*, vol. 10, no. 19, pp. 4662–4670, 2019, doi: 10.7150/jca.29280.
- [48] A. De Blasio, R. Vento, and R. Di Fiore, 'Mcl-1 targeting could be an intriguing perspective to cure cancer', *J Cell Physiol*, vol. 233, no. 11, pp. 8482–8498, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1002/jcp.26786.
- [49] H. Mao, Q. Huang, and Y. Liu, 'MEG3 aggravates hypoxia/reoxygenation induced apoptosis of renal tubular epithelial cells via the miR-129-5p/HMGB1 axis', *J Biochem Mol Toxicol*, vol. 35, no. 2, p. e22649, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1002/jbt.22649.
- [50] H. Zhou *et al.*, 'Regulatory Network of Two Tumor-Suppressive Noncoding RNAs Interferes with the Growth and Metastasis of Renal Cell Carcinoma', *Mol Ther Nucleic Acids*, vol. 16, pp. 554–565, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.omtn.2019.04.005.

- [51] A. Gong *et al.*, 'The lncRNA MEG3 mediates renal cell cancer progression by regulating ST3Gal1 transcription and EGFR sialylation', *J Cell Sci*, vol. 133, no. 16, p. jcs244020, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1242/jcs.244020.
- [52] J. Ding *et al.*, 'Estrogen receptor β promotes renal cell carcinoma progression via regulating LncRNA HOTAIR-miR-138/200c/204/217 associated CeRNA network', *Oncogene*, vol. 37, no. 37, pp. 5037–5053, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41388-018-0175-6.